

Publishing and sharing sensitive data

Australian Research Data Commons

When and how to publish sensitive data as openly and ethically as possible.

For more information see: ardc.edu.au/resources/working-with-data

Sensitive data identifies individuals, species, objects or locations, and carries a risk of causing discrimination, harm or unwanted attention.

PUBLISHING AND SHARING

Keep in mind

- Make your data as FAIR as possible (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).
- Publish your data and metadata according to participant consent, ethics approval and licensing.
- For sensitive data, it is often appropriate to have public metadata and conditional access to the data whose risk of identifiability has been managed.
- Cite your data along with your other scholarly outputs.